

Surgery of a Mature Thoracic Teratoma : (Radiological Image)

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OBSERVATION

A 57-year-old female patient, with no notable medical history, presented with a persistent dry cough for the past six months. Initial clinical examination revealed no significant abnormalities. Subsequently, a thoracic radiograph demonstrated a right paracardiac opacity obscuring the right border of the heart (Figure 1). Thoracic CT with contrast enhancement revealed the presence of a right paracardiac mass with heterogeneous tissue composition and internal calcifications, suggestive of a mature teratoma (Figure 2). Surgical resection of the mass was performed, and macroscopic examination confirmed its encapsulated nature, with the presence of hairs within, supporting the diagnosis of a mature teratoma (Figure 3).

Figure 1 : Heterogeneous Right Paracardiac Opacity obscuring the Right Border of the Heart.

Figure 2 : CT Scan Slices Showing a right paracardiac tumor with heterogeneous tissue composition and internal calcifications.

Figure 3 : Surgical Specimen Revealing an Encapsulated Mass with Presence of Hair Inside.